

Working Conditions and Job Satisfaction of Audio Describers in China

Information Form

We are an international academic team focused on improving the quality of audio description services. We have carefully designed an **online survey** to understand the **working conditions and job satisfaction of audio describers in Mainland China, Hong Kong, Macao, and Taiwan**. This will enhance the international academic community's understanding of the current state of audio description (AD) development in these areas. The survey is conducted through the QUALTRICS platform and is expected to take 10-15 minutes to complete.

We sincerely invite you to participate in this study. Please take some time out of your busy schedule to help us complete the survey, and feel free to distribute it to colleagues within your institution. This will help us gather more information, thus allowing a more comprehensive understanding of the situation of audio describers in Mainland China, Hong Kong, Macao, and Taiwan.

We will not collect any personal information from you; your participation will be **anonymous**. The data collected will be used by researchers to organize data sets, write papers, and make presentations. To fully utilize the collected data, it may be used for other research purposes in the future. Your participation in this study is entirely voluntary; you have the right to refuse or withdraw at any time without explanation and without any adverse consequences.

This research has been reviewed by the Ethics Committee for Humanities and Social Sciences at the University of Antwerp (Project Number: SHW_2022_32_1).

If you have any questions about this study, please contact:

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Thank you for reading and understanding this information form.

Consent Form

I confirm that I have read and understood the **Information Form**. I was given sufficient time to consider the information and to ask questions, to which I have received adequate answers.

I have fully understood that I can discontinue my participation in this study at any time without this having any disadvantages.

I am aware of the goal for which the data provided by me will be collected, processed and used within the framework of this study and that they will be treated in a confidential manner.

I agree to the collection, processing and use of these data, as described in the information sheet for the participant.

I agree to the reuse of the research data provided by me for other research purposes. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

I am willing to provide information regarding my participation in possible follow-up studies.

For this study we are working with QUALTRICS. Please be informed about the privacy policy and potential recent updates before you agree to participate in our study. You can find this information here: <https://www.qualtrics.com/privacy-statement/>.

Do you agree with the QUALTRICS privacy statement?

Yes, I am over 18 years old, have read the Qualtrics privacy statement and agree with their policies.

No, I have not read the Qualtrics privacy statement and/or do not agree with their policies.

Background Information

What is the highest level of education you have achieved or are currently pursuing?

- Primary
- Secondary
- High school
- Vocational education
- BA/BSc
- MA/MSc
- PhD

What is your educational background? [multiple answers possible]

- Language and linguistics
 - Literature
 - Translation
 - Film and TV studies
 - Theatre studies
 - Broadcasting and Hosting Arts
 - Museum studies
 - Psychology
 - Journalism or media studies
 - Science
 - Computer science and IT
 - Other, please specify:
-

What is your age?

- 18 – 25
- 26 – 35
- 36 – 45
- 46 – 55
- 56 – 65
- 66 and over

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

How long have you been working as an audio describer (in any area of AD, e.g., film, TV, live events)?

- Less than 1 year
- 1-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- Over 15 years

Which of the following AD types have you worked with the most in the last 5 years? [multiple answers possible]

- Film
 - TV
 - Theatre
 - Opera
 - Museum
 - Other live events
 - Other, please specify:
-

Which of the following work stages have you participated in (can be in any area of AD, such as films, TV, live events/real-time events)? [multiple answers possible]

- Writing and/or revising AD scripts
 - Translating AD scripts
 - Voicing AD
 - Assisting at recording AD with voice talents
 - Mixing audio description with the original soundtrack (post-production)
 - Quality control of the product (e.g., checking scripts, translations, recordings, soundtracks, etc.)
 - Other, please specify:
-

What job title(s) do you use for yourself?

- AD Scriptwriter
 - Audio Describer
 - Narrator
 - Commentator
 - Accessible Filmmaker
 - Translator
 - Other, please specify:
-

Where do you live?

- Mainland China
- Hong Kong
- Macao
- Taiwan

Display This Question:

If Where do you live? = Mainland China

If you reside in Mainland China, in which province, autonomous region or municipality do you live?

- Beijing
- Tianjin
- Hebei
- Shanxi
- Inner Mongolia
- Liaoning
- Jilin
- Heilongjiang
- Shanghai
- Jiangsu
- Zhejiang
- Anhui
- Fujian
- Jiangxi
- Shandong
- Henan
- Hubei
- Hunan
- Guangdong

- Guangxi
- Hainan
- Chongqing
- Sichuan
- Guizhou
- Yunnan
- Tibet
- Shaanxi
- Gansu
- Qinghai
- Ningxia
- Xinjiang

In which language do you write scripts for AD?

- English
- Simplified Chinese
- Traditional Chinese
- Other, please specify: _____

Do you work for national or international clients? (Note: national clients are based in the country where you live)

- National
- International
- Both

Which of the following **best** describes your current employment status?

- Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]
- Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]
- Volunteer audio describer [Unpaid: Volunteer]

Working Conditions

Have you received specialized training before providing AD services?

- Yes
- No

Display This Question:

If Have you received specialized training before providing AD services? = Yes

If yes, in what form? (multiple answers possible)

- Workshop
 - Vocational course
 - University course
 - Internship
 - In-house training
 - One-to-one instruction
 - Online course
 - Other, please specify:
-

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

Or Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

Does your client provide you with opportunities to continue your professional development? (e.g., courses, workshops etc.)

- Yes
- No

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Volunteer audio describer [Unpaid: Volunteer]

Do you take part in any professional development activities after joining the AD volunteer service? (e.g., courses, workshops etc.)

Yes

No

Display This Question:

If Does your client provide you with opportunities to continue your professional development? (e.g.,... = Yes

Or Do you take part in any professional development activities after joining the AD volunteer servic... = Yes

If yes, what are they?

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

Or Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

What percentage of your income comes from AD assignments?

Less than 25%

25-50%

51-75%

More than 75%

I don't know

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Volunteer audio describer [Unpaid: Volunteer]

What percentage of your work time do you dedicate to AD assignments?

- Less than 25%
- 25-50%
- 51-75%
- More than 75%
- I don't know

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

Or Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

Are you satisfied with your income level?

- Very dissatisfied
- Fairly dissatisfied
- Neither satisfied not dissatisfied
- Fairly satisfied
- Very satisfied

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

Or Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

To what extent can you influence the following?

	To a very low degree or not at all	To a low degree	To a certain degree	To a high degree	To a very high degree
Your working hours	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The clients you work for	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The AD tasks you accept	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Your fees or your income level	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The quality of the completed AD task	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Volunteer audio describer
[Unpaid: Volunteer]

To what extent can you influence the following?

	To a very low degree or not at all	To a low degree	To a certain degree	To a high degree	To a very high degree
The commissioners you work for	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The AD tasks you accept	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The amount of time you invest in AD tasks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The quality of the completed AD task	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How often do you have to compromise the quality of your work due to external factors (such as deadlines)?

- Never
- Occasionally
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- Always

How often have you experienced negative work-related stress in the past year?

- Never
- Occasionally
- Monthly
- Weekly
- Daily

Display This Question:

If How often have you experienced negative work-related stress in the past year? != Never

And Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

What are the main causes of stress? (multiple answers possible)

- Tight deadlines
 - Unfair payment
 - Interactions with colleagues
 - Interactions with clients
 - Lack of feedback
 - Unsuitable workspace
 - Unsuitable work equipment
 - Other, please specify:
-

Display This Question:

If How often have you experienced negative work-related stress in the past year? != Never

And Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

What are the main causes of stress? (multiple answers possible)

- Tight deadlines
 - Unfair payment
 - Interactions with clients
 - Other, please specify:
-

Display This Question:

If How often have you experienced negative work-related stress in the past year? != Never

And Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Volunteer audio describer [Unpaid: Volunteer]

What are the main causes of stress? (multiple answers possible)

- Tight deadlines
 - Interactions with the commissioner
 - Other, please specify:
-

How often have you considered leaving this industry in the past year?

- Never
- Occasionally
- Monthly
- Weekly
- Daily

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

Or Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

How often do you discuss AD issues with the following people?

	Never	Occasionally	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
Other audio describers	<input type="radio"/>				
Blind and partially sighted patrons?	<input type="radio"/>				
Clients?	<input type="radio"/>				

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Volunteer audio describer [Unpaid: Volunteer]

How often do you discuss AD issues with the following people?

	Never	Occasionally	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
Other audio describers	<input type="radio"/>				
Blind and partially sighted patrons	<input type="radio"/>				
Your commissioner	<input type="radio"/>				

How often do you receive feedback on the quality of your work?

- Never
- Occasionally
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- Always

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

Or Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

Do your clients trust the quality of your work?

- To a very low degree or not at all
- To a low degree
- To a certain degree
- To a high degree
- To a very high degree
- I don't know

Display This Question:

*If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Volunteer audio describer
[Unpaid: Volunteer]*

Does your commissioner trust the quality of your work?

- To a very low degree or not at all
- To a low degree
- To a certain degree
- To a high degree
- To a very high degree
- I don't know

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Employed]

Or Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Professional audio describer [Paid: Freelancer]

Do your clients consider your work important?

- To a very low degree or not at all
- To a low degree
- To a certain degree
- To a high degree
- To a very high degree
- I don't know

Display This Question:

If Which of the following best describes your current employment status? = Volunteer audio describer [Unpaid: Volunteer]

Does your commissioner consider your work important?

- To a very low degree or not at all
- To a low degree
- To a certain degree
- To a high degree
- To a very high degree
- I don't know

Where do you usually work?

- Home office (e.g., study room)
- Other rooms at home (e.g., bedroom, living room)
- Office outside my home
- School dormitory
- Library
- Other, please specify:

Do you share your office?

- No, I work alone
- Yes, with 1 person
- Yes, with 2-4 people
- Yes, with 5-9 people
- Yes, with 10 people or more

Do you have a dedicated workspace (i.e., a desk/table not shared with anyone else or used for any other function)?

- Yes
- No

Which software do you use to complete your AD assignments? (multiple answers possible)

- Text editor
- Voice recording software
- Video editing software
- Subtitling software
- Specific AD software
- CAT tools
- Other, please specify:

Do you have enough time for yourself or your family outside of work?

- Never
- Occasionally
- Sometimes
- Most of the time
- Always

Professional Image

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	To a very low degree or not at all	To a low degree	To a certain degree	To a high degree	To a very high degree
AD involves creativity.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AD requires expert skills.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
AD is a prestigious job.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Audio describers are visible as a working group in society.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The work of an audio describer has an economic, political or social impact.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Audio describers are valued in society.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Job Satisfaction

We would like to know how you feel about your present job, what things you are satisfied with and what things you are not satisfied with. On my present job, this is how I feel about...

	Not satisfied	Somewhat satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied	Extremely satisfied
The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities	<input type="radio"/>				
The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	<input type="radio"/>				
My pay and the amount of work I do	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to work alone on the job	<input type="radio"/>				
Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience	<input type="radio"/>				
The freedom to use my own judgment	<input type="radio"/>				
The way my job provides for steady employment	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to be "somebody" in the community	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to do things for other people	<input type="radio"/>				
The chance to do different things from time to time	<input type="radio"/>				

The working
conditions

Considering all aspects of your job, how satisfied are you overall?

- Not satisfied
- Somewhat dissatisfied
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied
- Extremely satisfied

Do you have any additional comments regarding the topics covered in this survey?
